

Church, Assimilation and Economic Outcomes: The Eastern Orthodox Church in the US

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THE ECONOMICS OF MIGRATION 57811
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This paper examines the impact of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches on immigrant assimilation in the United States, focusing on the roles of human capital and social capital. These churches, which maintain strong cultural and community ties to immigrants' countries of origin, influence assimilation by providing social networks and community support. On the one hand, they contribute to social capital by fostering connections within the ethnic community. On the other hand, they affect human capital, such as language acquisition and access to labor market opportunities. Using county-level data on the geographic distribution of Russian Orthodox churches and applying a difference-in-differences approach, we analyze how the presence of these churches impacts social, civic, economic, and cultural assimilation outcomes for immigrants. This study provides insights into the dual role of ethnic religious institutions in both supporting and sometimes slowing down aspects of the integration process.

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This paper examines the impact of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches on immigrant assimilation in the United States, focusing on the roles of human capital and social capital. These churches, which maintain strong cultural and community ties to immigrants' countries of origin, influence assimilation by providing social networks and community support. On the one hand, they contribute to social capital by fostering connections within the ethnic community. On the other hand, they affect human capital, such as language acquisition and access to labor market opportunities. Using county-level data on the geographic distribution of Russian Orthodox churches and applying a difference-in-differences approach, we analyze how the presence of these churches impacts social, civic, economic, and cultural assimilation outcomes for immigrants. This study provides insights into the dual role of ethnic religious institutions in both supporting and sometimes slowing down aspects of the integration process.

Immigration has profoundly shaped the social and economic fabric of the United States, bringing diverse cultures and communities into close contact. Among the myriad factors influencing the assimilation of immigrants, ethnic religious institutions stand out as particularly significant. These institutions often serve as pivotal support networks, providing newcomers with a sense of community and continuity amidst the challenges of adapting to a new society. However, they may also reinforce ethnic identities in ways that complicate integration into the broader social fabric. The Eastern Orthodox Church, uniquely organized along ethnic lines, offers a compelling context for examining these dynamics.

Assimilation is a multifaceted process involving social, economic, cultural, and civic dimensions. Human capital—encompassing skills, education, and abilities—plays a critical role in economic integration. Yet, immigrants frequently experience a depreciation of their human capital due to language barriers, non-recognition of foreign credentials, and cultural differences. Social capital, defined by the networks and relationships that provide access to resources and support,

* Data and code for replication available at <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/PGDEH>
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becomes essential in mitigating these challenges. Ethnic religious communities often embody this social capital, facilitating information sharing and offering immediate support to immigrants navigating their new environment.

This study investigates the dualistic role of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches in the assimilation of immigrants and their descendants in the United States. While these churches provide crucial support to first-generation immigrants, they may also inadvertently impede the long-term integration of subsequent generations by reinforcing strong intra-group ties. Understanding this paradox is vital for comprehending the broader patterns of immigrant assimilation and the factors that facilitate or hinder integration.

Building upon the work of Gagliarducci and Tabellini on Italian immigrants in the United States, this research replicates and extends their analysis within the context of Eastern European immigrant communities. By focusing on the Eastern Orthodox Church—a religious institution that maintains strong ethnic identities while sharing a common faith—we aim to disentangle the effects of ethnic community support from those of religious affiliation on immigrant assimilation.

The central research question guiding this study is: How does the presence of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches affect the assimilation outcomes of immigrants and their descendants in the United States? Specifically, we examine whether these ethnic religious institutions serve primarily as bonding social capital that strengthens intra-group cohesion at the expense of broader societal integration, or as bridging social capital that connects individuals across diverse social cleavages.

We hypothesize that the presence of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches facilitates the initial economic and social adjustment of first-generation immigrants by providing essential support and preserving cultural traditions. However, for second-generation immigrants, these same institutions may impose constraints on assimilation by reinforcing ethnic identities and limiting exposure to diverse social networks. The strong expectations of group loyalty and adherence to traditional norms within these communities may inhibit the acquisition of new forms of human capital valued in the wider labor market.

To explore these hypotheses, we utilize data from the American Community Survey (ACS) and the U.S. Religion Census. The ACS provides detailed socioeconomic and demographic information on immigrants, allowing us to measure various dimensions of assimilation, including intermarriage rates, English proficiency, naturalization status, labor force participation, and occupational outcomes. The Religion Census offers comprehensive data on the presence and distribution of ethnic Orthodox churches across U.S. counties.

Our empirical strategy involves comparing assimilation outcomes of immigrants from specific ethnicities in counties with and without ethnic Orthodox churches corresponding to their ethnic backgrounds. By incorporating county, year, and ethnicity fixed effects in our regression models, we control for unobserved heterogeneity and isolate the impact of ethnic church presence on assimilation outcomes. Additionally, we examine generational differences by interacting church presence

with an indicator for being U.S.-born, thereby assessing whether the effects vary between first and second-generation immigrants.

findings

Methodologically, this research addresses potential concerns related to selection bias and unobserved confounding factors by employing fixed-effects models and instrumental variable approaches. Nevertheless, we acknowledge limitations, such as the challenges of fully capturing the causal relationships and the complexities inherent in measuring assimilation across diverse dimensions.

In connecting to broader themes within the field, this study contributes to ongoing debates regarding the roles of bonding and bridging social capital in immigrant integration. It highlights the need for a nuanced understanding of how ethnic institutions shape the assimilation trajectories of different generations. By focusing on the Eastern Orthodox Church, we shed light on a relatively understudied context, enriching the literature on immigration, assimilation, and the interplay between cultural preservation and societal integration.

The paper proceeds as follows: We begin with a detailed historical context of the Eastern Orthodox Church in the United States, outlining its unique organizational structure and its implications for immigrant communities. Next, we describe our data sources and empirical strategy, elaborating on the construction of variables and the methods employed to address potential methodological challenges. We then present our empirical results, discussing their significance in relation to our hypotheses and the existing literature. Finally, we conclude with a discussion of the broader implications of our findings and suggestions for future research.

I. Theoretical Framework

The Idea of Human capital refers to the skills, education, and abilities that enhance an individual's productivity and capabilities. during migration, immigrants often experience a negative shock of their human capital due to language barriers, non-recognition of foreign credentials, and cultural differences. That shock necessitates a period of adjustment and rebuilding as immigrants seek to restore their economic and social standing. (Weiss, Sauer and Gotlibovski, 2003)

To mitigate the loss of human capital, immigrants frequently turn to similiar social networks that provide access to resources and support. these networks facilitate 'pull' of human capital, by which the immigrant can access resources and information, those network are often referd as 'Social Capital'. Social capital facilitates information sharing about opportunities, thereby reducing transaction costs associated with settling into a new environment. This reliance on social capital is seen in the phenomenon of the "New World effect," where immigrants tend to cluster in areas previously settled by earlier waves of their ethnic group, a pattern well documented in migration studies.(Abramitzky, Boustan and Eriksson, 2014)

Religious communities, particularly ethnic religious communities, are often at the center of this social capital dynamic. These communities offer immigrants a

familiar cultural and linguistic environment that helps ease their transition into a new country. Membership in local immigrant communities provides immediate access to valuable social networks, resources, and information that are crucial during the initial stages of migration. (Murphy, Nourani and Lee, 2022) Such communities often offer employment opportunities and social support, helping to bridge the gaps that arise from the loss of human capital. (Lórinz and Németh, 2022) However, even though in some cases, ethnic communities function as a bridge to broader society, in others, they may create a "lock-in" effect that slows down the integration process.

The "lock-in" effect is tied to the concept of "bonding" versus "bridging" social capital. Bonding social capital refers to the strong ties within a homogeneous group, reinforcing shared identities and providing mutual support. on the other hand, Bridging social capital, connects individuals across diverse social groups, fostering inclusivity and facilitating integration into the broader society. (Patulny and Svendsen, 2007; Lórinz and Németh, 2022)

Local communities of immigrants can create a path dependence trajectories, where quick access to bonding social capital immediately after migration offers short-term benefits, but may lead to long-term challenges in integrating into broader networks. This dynamic creates an intertemporal decision problem for immigrants, where their choice of community affiliation hinges on their discount rate for community membership costs and returns.

For first-generation immigrants, the bonding social capital found in ethnic religious communities is invaluable. It offers immediate economic and social benefits by connecting individuals with others who share their language, culture, and experiences. This network facilitates access to employment within the ethnic enclave, provides mutual aid, and helps preserve cultural traditions. The strong intra-group cohesion reduces uncertainties and risks associated with migration, effectively acting as a support system that compensates for the loss of human capital.

However, second-generation immigrants may find that the same bonding social capital imposes constraints, The strong expectations of group loyalty and adherence to traditional cultural norms can create barriers to integration into the broader society, The community's emphasis on preserving ethnic identity may limit exposure to diverse social networks and inhibit the acquisition of new forms of human capital valued in the wider labor market. High "switching costs" associated with breaking away from the community—such as familial pressure and loss of support networks—can discourage second-generation immigrants from pursuing broader integration paths. (Min, 2010)

Our theoretical framework suggests that, while ethnic religious communities provide essential support to first-generation immigrants, they may create a "lock-in" effect, making it increasingly difficult for second-generation immigrants to integrate fully into the host society. The initial reliance on ethnic communities can lead to a path-dependent process, where early choices set a trajectory af-

fecting subsequent generations. Path dependence implies that initial decisions have long-lasting effects due to increasing returns and the cumulative nature of social processes. Those may be found in high "switching costs" associated with breaking away from the community—such as familial pressure and loss of support networks—can discourage second-generation immigrants from pursuing broader integration paths.

A. *Historical Context: The Eastern Orthodox Church*

The case of Eastern Orthodox Church in the United States provides a unique context for examining the impact of ethnic religious communities on immigrant integration. Unlike other Christian denominations that have largely moved toward integrated structures, the Orthodox Church has maintained its organization along ethnic lines, with jurisdictions corresponding to national origins. This structure reinforces ethnic identities and creates distinct communities within the broader Orthodox faith. The hierarchical structure of the Orthodox Church, the use of traditional liturgical languages, and the incorporation of ethnic cultural elements into religious practice further underscore the ethnic character of these institutions. (Krindatch, n.d.)

The persistence of ethnic divisions within American Orthodoxy, stemming from historical developments like the Bolshevik Revolution and waves of immigration from Eastern and Southern Europe, has led to a "path dependence" routes in which immigrant descendants maintain ethnic ties through religious affiliation. This phenomenon can be observed in the continued ethnic identity of Serbian Orthodox or Russian Orthodox parishes that serve not only recent immigrants but also descendants of those who arrived over a century ago. (Krindatch, 2011)

This structure raises critical questions about how these ethnic religious communities affect immigrant integration across generations and the extent to which they function as sources of bonding versus bridging social capital. Previous research has explored the relationship between ethnic religious institutions and immigrant integration. For instance, Gagliarducci and Tabellini (2022) found that the presence of Italian churches during the Great Migration was associated with lower rates of intermarriage and naturalization among Italian immigrants.

We follow a similar approach to examine the effect of presence of ethnic church on integration, but rather than focusing on one specific group, we examine the effect of multiple ethnic groups that share the same beliefs and church but differ in the ethnicity of their congregation. Our Paper tries to isolate the effects of these ethnic religious institutions on immigrant integration outcomes by utilizing the variation of multiple ethnic orthodox churches, helps us to separate the impact of ethnic identity from the general religious component.

II. Data

Our study explores the relationship between ethnic religious institutions and immigrant assimilation in the United States by utilizing a combination of three

key data sources. First, we rely on the American Community Survey (ACS) for the years 2000, 2010, and 2020 to gather our primary outcome variables as well as the main control variables. The ACS, conducted annually by the U.S. Census Bureau, is a widely used resource that provides comprehensive information on various topics such as employment, education, income, language proficiency, migration, and housing characteristics. In the context of our research, the ACS allows us to identify immigrants, their countries of origin, and several demographic variables essential for measuring assimilation.

Second, we incorporate data from the Religion Census conducted by the Association of Statisticians of American Religious Bodies (ASARB). This dataset, available for the same years as the ACS—2000, 2010, and 2020—offers detailed insights into religious institutions and adherents across the U.S. Our primary explanatory variable, the number of Orthodox Christian congregations in each county, is drawn from this data. The ASARB data is critical in assessing the influence of Orthodox churches on immigrant assimilation by providing a direct measure of religious presence at the local level.

Third, for our historical instrument variable analysis, we utilize the 1936 Census of Religious Bodies (CRB), a survey conducted by the U.S. Census Bureau from 1906 to 1946. The CRB gathered extensive data on religious congregations, including membership demographics, denominational affiliations, and clergy information. The 1936 CRB data offers a historical snapshot of the religious landscape in the United States, allowing us to use the presence of Orthodox Christian congregations during that period as an instrumental variable. Specifically, we employ the number of Orthodox churches in 1936 as a proxy to predict the presence of Orthodox churches in 2020, enabling us to address potential endogeneity in our analysis.

In this study, we construct several proxies for immigrant assimilation, drawing inspiration from the work of Tabellini. Our approach begins by assessing social assimilation through indicators such as intermarriage between immigrants and native-born U.S. citizens of native parentage, as well as the ability to speak English. For English proficiency, we consider individuals who are at least 15 years old to ensure that the sample reflects mature language use in social and professional settings. Additionally, we examine naturalization rates as another proxy for social assimilation, focusing specifically on immigrant men aged 21 and older who have resided in the U.S. for at least five years, as this group meets the eligibility criteria for citizenship. These social assimilation indicators help us capture both cultural and legal aspects of integration.

To measure economic assimilation, we use wage elasticity, which reflects the intergenerational transmission of wages. This measure captures the extent to which children’s wages are correlated with their parents’ wages, with higher wage elasticity indicating stronger economic assimilation. This proxy allows us to explore how economic outcomes evolve across generations within immigrant families.

Our key explanatory variable, the number of Orthodox church congregations

in each county, is drawn from the ASARB Religion Census for the years 2000, 2010, and 2020. The presence of these ethnic congregations serves as a proxy for the influence of ethnic religious institutions on the local immigrant community. We develop an Ethnic Church Classification by identifying Orthodox Christian denominations associated with specific ethnicities, such as Russian, Serbian, and Ukrainian Orthodox churches. In our analysis, we focus on European-origin Orthodox churches, excluding those from Ethiopia, Eritrea, and Jordan, to maintain consistency in the study's scope. For counties that do not appear in the Religion Census, we assume the absence of Orthodox congregations.

Our final sample includes Orthodox churches from several ethnicities, such as Russian, Ukrainian, Serbian, Albanian, Macedonian, Armenian, Romanian, and Bulgarian. Notably, within the Russian community, two affiliated churches exist: the Russian Orthodox Church (ROC) and the Russian Orthodox Church Outside of Russia (ROCOR). Despite their differences, we include both in our analysis as equivalent entities.

For our outcome variables, we construct several proxies for social assimilation using ACS data. One proxy is intermarriage, defined as a marriage between an immigrant and a U.S.-born citizen of native parentage. This variable is coded as a binary outcome, with a value of one indicating that the individual is married to a U.S.-born citizen, and zero otherwise. Another key variable, inspired by Tabellini, is naturalization status, which is also coded as a binary outcome, with one indicating that the individual is a U.S. citizen (either native-born or naturalized), and zero indicating non-citizenship. English proficiency serves as a final social assimilation proxy, with a dummy variable indicating whether an individual speaks English well or exclusively. To ensure meaningful results, we limit the sample for intermarriage to individuals aged 15 and older.

For first-generation immigrants, we restrict the sample to those aged 21 and older who have resided in the U.S. for at least five years, aligning with citizenship eligibility requirements. All U.S.-born children of immigrants are included in the sample, reflecting the *jus soli* policy that grants birthright citizenship. To assess economic assimilation, we rely on the log of wages, measuring the correlation between children's and parents' wages. Higher wage elasticity, indicating stronger economic ties between generations, is used as our proxy for economic integration. We excluded an alternative measure of occupational income score, as it did not demonstrate significant effects in our analysis.

We also incorporate interaction terms between church presence and U.S.-born status to examine generational differences in the influence of Orthodox churches on intergenerational assimilation patterns. This allows us to test our hypothesis that church presence may have varying effects depending on whether individuals are first- or second-generation immigrants.

For our main regressor, we use the number of ethnic Orthodox church congregations in each county for each year and ethnic group. This variable serves as a proxy for the influence of the church on local communities. We include a

range of control variables at both the individual and county levels. Individual-level controls include household size, age at migration, years of marriage, years of education, and age. At the county level, we control for the total number of congregations, adherents across all religious denominations, unemployment rates, average wages, and the share of immigrants. These controls help account for the broader religious and economic environment that may influence assimilation outcomes.

We create additional variables to match individuals to ethnic churches based on their country of origin. For the Religion Census, we match churches to ethnic groups using the name of the church and denomination (e.g., “Serbian Orthodox”). For the ACS, we match country of origin by the birthplace of individuals and their parents. These individual-ethnic matching variables help distinguish first- and second-generation immigrants. After filtering out immigrants from non-European countries, we assign ethnicity based on the father’s ethnic background if available. For remaining cases, we rely on the mother’s ethnicity. Observations without identifiable ethnicities are dropped from the sample.

We merge the ACS and Religion Census datasets at the county level using FIPS codes, matching by year, county, and ethnicity. The resulting dataset is then merged with the 1936 CRB data to incorporate historical church presence as an instrumental variable. Finally, we construct an instrument variable for church presence in 2020 by using the 1936 CRB data. Counties with at least one Orthodox church in 1936 are assigned a distance of zero from a historical church. For all other counties, we calculate the distance to the nearest 1936 church by measuring the minimum distance between county centroids. This distance variable allows us to capture the potential historical influence of Orthodox churches on contemporary assimilation outcomes. The summary statistics for the variables used are in table (6) in the appendix, detailed table of Ethnicity matching is in table (7).

III. Empirical Strategy

Our empirical strategy aims to estimate the causal effect of ethnic church presence on assimilation outcomes—such as intermarriage rates, citizenship status, English proficiency, and wages—among first- and second-generation immigrants. A straightforward, naive approach, such as a simple Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression, would likely yield biased and inconsistent estimates due to several challenges. First, counties with larger immigrant populations may be more likely to establish ethnic churches, and these larger communities may have different assimilation patterns, driven by social support networks or community size effects. Second, counties may differ significantly in terms of local policies, cultural attitudes, or economic conditions—factors that are unobserved in the naive model and could confound the relationship between church presence and assimilation outcomes. Additionally, there is the risk of reverse causality, where lower levels of assimilation could lead to the establishment of ethnic churches as a

means of preserving cultural identity, instead of ethnic churches driving changes in assimilation.

To address those issues we employ a Difference-in-Differences approach by including time and county fixed effects. that leverages variation across counties and time, County fixed effects capture time-invariant characteristics specific to each county, The year fixed effects control for time-specific shocks or trends that affect all counties, while the county fixed effects account for unobserved, time-invariant characteristics specific to each county. This allows us to compare changes in assimilation outcomes over time within each county, thereby isolating the impact of ethnic church presence. Given that different ethnic groups may have varying propensities to establish ethnic churches and may follow distinct assimilation trajectories, we include ethnicity-specific fixed effects to control for time-invariant differences across ethnicities.

Our baseline model is specified as follows

$$(1) \quad y_{iect} = \alpha_c + \gamma_t + \delta_e + \beta_1 \text{Church}_{ect} + \mathbf{X}_{ict} \boldsymbol{\gamma} + \varepsilon_{iect}$$

In this model, y_{iect} represents the assimilation outcome for individual i of ethnicity e residing in county c at census year t . The assimilation outcomes considered include intermarriage rates, citizenship status, English proficiency, and log wage. The variable Church_{ect} corresponds to the number of congregations of ethnicity e background are present in county c at time t .

α_c represents county fixed effects, which capture all unobserved, time-invariant characteristics specific to county c . These characteristics may include geographic features, local policies, or cultural norms that do not vary over time. γ_t denotes year fixed effects, which account for shocks or trends common to all counties at time t , such as national economic conditions, by including both we formulate diff in diff spciefication. The vector \mathbf{X}_{ict} includes individual-level control variables, such as household size, age at migration, years married, years of education, age, age squared, year of immigration, and parental immigration years. he coefficient vector $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ is associated with the control variables, while ε_{iect} represents the error term, capturing unobserved factors affecting assimilation outcomes. δ_e represents ethnicity fixed effects, which capture unobserved, time-invariant characteristics specific to ethnicity e . These characteristics includes ethnic specific assimilation trajectories.

for the second generation we include an interaction term between church presence and an indicator for U.S.-born status to examine generational differences:

$$(2) \quad y_{iect} = \alpha_c + \gamma_t + \beta_1 \text{Church}_{ect} + \beta_2 \text{USBorn}_i + \beta_3 (\text{USBorn}_i \times \text{Church}_{ect}) + \mathbf{X}_{ict} \boldsymbol{\gamma} + \varepsilon_{iect}$$

Our empirical strategy leverages the DiD framework to exploit the variation across counties with and without ethnic churches over different time periods. The central identification assumption the parallel terns assumption is in our context that in the absence of ethnic church presence, assimilation outcomes would have

followed similar trends in both types of counties. However, potential biases may still arise if there are time-varying, unobserved factors that are correlated with both church presence and assimilation outcomes. For example, if counties with lower levels of assimilation are more likely to establish ethnic churches as a way to preserve cultural identity or strengthen community support, this could violate the parallel trends assumption. In such cases, the relationship between church presence and assimilation may be confounded by these unobserved factors, leading to biased estimates.

However, we may still encounter potential biases if there are time-varying, unobserved factors that are systematically correlated with both ethnic church presence and assimilation outcomes. For instance, if counties with lower assimilation levels are more likely to establish ethnic churches in response to their need for cultural preservation or community support, this could violate the parallel trends assumption. While this reduces concerns related to ethnic heterogeneity, it may not fully account for time-varying ethnic-specific factors, and we still have concerns of endogeneity.

To address those concerns we use lagged church presence as an instrument for current church presence, based on the assumption that past church presence affects current assimilation outcomes only through its influence on current church presence. By using lagged church presence, we avoid reverse causality since current assimilation outcomes cannot influence past church presence. The predicted values from the first-stage regression (based on lagged values) represent the exogenous component of current church presence, isolating the part driven by historical factors rather than contemporary assimilation outcomes or shocks.

The lagged values capture the historical persistence of church presence, as the number of ethnic churches in a county in the past is unlikely to be affected by current outcomes such as intermarriage rates, citizenship status, or wages. This makes the lagged church presence a valid instrument. The fitted values from the first-stage model represent the portion of current church presence that can be explained by its past levels, rather than by unobserved, time-varying factors that might affect both church presence and assimilation outcomes. Since these fitted values are based on past information that is exogenous to current-period shocks, they help isolate variation in church presence that is unrelated to unobserved factors influencing current assimilation outcomes.

Specifically, we instrument current ethnic church presence with its lagged value. The underlying assumption is that past church presence affects current assimilation outcomes only through its influence on current church presence, thus providing exogenous variation in church presence. The first-stage regression of the two-stage least squares (2SLS) estimation is specified as:

$$(3) \quad \text{Church}_{ect} = \pi_0 + \pi_1 \text{LagChurch}_{ect} + \alpha_c + \gamma_t + \boldsymbol{\pi}_2 \mathbf{Z}_{ct} + \eta_{ect}$$

In this equation, LagChurch_{ect} is the lagged value of the church presence indi-

cator, and \mathbf{Z}_{ct} includes county-level controls such as average log wage, percentage of Black population, percentage of immigrant population, and average occupational score. The coefficient π_1 measures the strength of the relationship between lagged and current church presence. The validity of the instrument relies on two key assumptions: relevance and exclusion restriction. The relevance assumption requires that lagged church presence is a strong predictor of current church presence ($\pi_1 \neq 0$), while the exclusion restriction requires that lagged church presence affects current assimilation outcomes only through its effect on current church presence, not through any other channels. A significant π_1 in the first-stage regression confirms the relevance of the instrument.

The second-stage regression uses the predicted values of church presence from the first stage to estimate the effect on assimilation outcomes:

$$(4) \quad y_{iect} = \alpha_c + \gamma_t + \beta_1 \widehat{Churc}_{ect} + \mathbf{X}_{ict}\boldsymbol{\gamma} + \varepsilon_{iect}$$

Here, \widehat{Churc}_{ect} represents the predicted church presence from the first-stage regression. The coefficient β_1 captures the causal effect of church presence on assimilation outcomes, assuming the instrument satisfies the relevance and exclusion restrictions. The IV estimates obtained from this approach address potential endogeneity concerns by isolating variation in church presence that is plausibly exogenous to current assimilation outcomes.

However, the exclusion restriction may be questioned if, for example, past church presence has a direct effect on current assimilation outcomes independent of current church presence. This concern is extremely plausible in our context, as the norms and institutions established by ethnic churches tend to have long-lasting and deep-rooted effects on the community. For example, ethnic churches often serve as critical hubs for social capital, fostering community networks and cultural practices that can persist even after the churches themselves may no longer be as active or prominent. These lasting effects could influence key assimilation outcomes, such as intermarriage rates, citizenship status, and cultural retention.

Moreover, ethnic churches may have historically shaped the educational opportunities, economic behaviors, and intergroup relationships within communities. These influences, rooted in the past, could continue to affect assimilation outcomes today, independent of the current physical presence of churches. For instance, social norms around family structure, language use, or cultural traditions may persist for generations, having been reinforced by past church activities. This potential long-term cultural impact of historical church presence challenges the validity of the exclusion restriction, as it implies that past church presence might have a direct and lingering effect on current assimilation outcomes, apart from its influence on current church presence.

To address concerns of endogeneity, we introduce an alternative instrument that

leverages historical church presence as a source of exogenous variation. Specifically, we use the distance from churches that existed in 1936 as an instrument for current church presence in 2020. The assumption underlying this instrument is that historical church presence affects current assimilation outcomes only through its influence on current church presence, thereby providing a valid source of exogenous variation.

The rationale for using distance as an instrument is that historical church locations were determined by factors from the past and are unlikely to be correlated with current unobserved factors affecting assimilation outcomes. Proximity to historical churches may influence current church presence due to historical settlement patterns, but should not directly affect current assimilation outcomes after controlling for observable factors. The location of churches in 1936 was likely influenced by geographic, demographic, and community-specific factors that were relevant at the time, such as immigrant clusters and their need for religious and social institutions. These historical factors are less likely to be directly correlated with current, time-varying factors affecting assimilation, such as modern local policies or economic conditions.

The second-stage regression is then specified as:

$$(5) \quad y_{iect} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \widehat{\text{Church}}_{ect} + \mathbf{X}_{ict} \boldsymbol{\gamma} + \varepsilon_{iect}$$

Using distance to historical churches as an instrument provides a source of exogenous variation in church presence that is uncorrelated with current unobserved factors, thus strengthening our identification strategy. The IV estimates obtained using this alternative instrument are presented in Table ??, and the first-stage F-statistics indicate the strength of the instrument. By employing both lagged church presence and distance to historical churches as instruments, we address potential endogeneity issues and provide robust evidence on the causal impact of ethnic church presence on assimilation outcomes.

However, there could be some potential concerns regarding the validity of the exclusion restriction. If the presence of a church in 1936 left a long-lasting cultural or social impact that directly shapes today's assimilation outcomes, the exclusion assumption might be violated. For example, historical churches may have created enduring community norms or social networks that could influence assimilation today, independent of current church presence. Similarly, if regions where churches were established in 1936 have retained strong immigrant communities over time, the factors influencing church presence may persist, and this could weaken the exclusion restriction. Despite these concerns, using distance to historical churches remains a strong instrument because it leverages historically determined locations that are unlikely to be directly related to current unobserved factors affecting assimilation outcomes, provided that we control for relevant modern factors and fixed effects.

IV. Results

A. Intermarriage

Table 1—: Intermarriage - Assimilation

	Intermarriage				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Church	-0.0006 (0.0007)	0.0024*** (0.0008)	0.0002 (0.0008)	0.0026*** (0.0009)	0.0003 (0.0008)
US-Born				16.05*** (2.484)	16.18*** (2.483)
Church \times US-Born				-0.0017 (0.0063)	-0.0012 (0.0063)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>					
County X Year		✓	✓	✓	✓
Ethnicity			✓		✓
R ²	0.2726	0.2879	0.2887	0.2891	0.2899
N	43,606	43,606	43,606	43,606	43,606

Notes: Standard errors are clustered at the county level. The ethnicity refers to immigrants who comes from one of the following countries of origin: Ukraine, Russia, Albania, Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia or Macedonia. Sample includes married individuals only, All models include year fixed effects. The dependent variable is Intermarriage, a Indicator variable for immigrant who married to a native-born spouse of native parentage. The key independent variable is Church, numeric continues variable for number of congregation of ethnicity in county. The sample includes married immigrants aged 15 or older. Models (2)-(5) include county fixed effects, and models (3) and (5) add ethnicity fixed effects. Models (4) and (5) include an interaction term between Church and US-Born.

Table 1 shows the results of the intermarriage model. In the baseline specification (Column 1), which includes individual and county-level controls, the coefficient on EthnicChurch is negative (-0.0006) but statistically insignificant. This suggests that, without accounting for time-specific factors or unobserved heterogeneity, the presence of ethnic churches does not significantly influence immigrants' likelihood of marrying outside their ethnic group.

However, when we introduce county and year fixed effects in a difference-in-differences framework (Column 2), the coefficient on EthnicChurch becomes positive (0.0024) and statistically significant at the 1% level. This indicates that each additional ethnic church congregation in a county is associated with a 0.24 percentage point increase in the probability of intermarriage among immigrants.

Given the average intermarriage rate in our sample, this effect is non-trivial and suggests that ethnic churches may, contrary to our initial hypothesis, facilitate social assimilation.

To explore generational differences, we include an interaction term between `EthnicChurch` and `US-Born` status (Column 4). The coefficient on `EthnicChurch` remains positive and significant (0.0026), while `US-Born` itself has a substantial positive coefficient (16.05), indicating that being born in the United States increases the probability of intermarriage by 16.05 percentage points compared to foreign-born immigrants. The interaction term `EthnicChurch` \times `US-Born` is negative (-0.0017) but statistically insignificant, suggesting that the effect of ethnic churches on intermarriage does not differ significantly between first-generation immigrants and their U.S.-born children.

These findings challenge our hypothesis that ethnic churches hinder assimilation by reinforcing ethnic identities and fostering insular communities. Instead, the positive association between ethnic church presence and intermarriage implies that these institutions may provide platforms for broader social interaction. One possible explanation is that ethnic churches, while preserving cultural traditions, also serve as communal spaces where immigrants engage with members of other ethnic groups, thereby increasing opportunities for interethnic relationships.

However, we must consider potential limitations. The positive effect may be influenced by unobserved factors correlated with both the establishment of ethnic churches and higher intermarriage rates, such as urbanization or socioeconomic diversity. Although county and year fixed effects control for time-invariant characteristics and common shocks, residual confounding variables might still bias our results.

Moreover, the lack of a significant interaction between `EthnicChurch` and `US-Born` suggests that the influence of ethnic churches on intermarriage is consistent across generations. This uniformity indicates that the mechanisms by which ethnic churches affect social assimilation operate similarly for both immigrants and their U.S.-born offspring.

In summary, our analysis reveals that the presence of ethnic Orthodox churches is associated with increased intermarriage rates among immigrants, suggesting a facilitative role in social assimilation. This finding invites further investigation into the specific functions of ethnic churches that may promote integration.

B. Income

Table (2) reports results of log wage as a proxy for economic assimilation. Here, the dependent variable is the natural log of the wage of individuals in our sample, and log parental income is included as a control variable, allowing us to isolate the influence of ethnic Orthodox churches on wages. The coefficient on log parental income measures intergenerational wage elasticity, representing how much a child's income is tied to their parents' income. This provides insights into intergenerational mobility, with a higher coefficient suggesting less mobility.

Table 2—: Income- Assimilation

Dep Variable: Model:	Log Wage				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Church	-0.0432** (0.0174)	-0.0546*** (0.0189)	-0.0236 (0.0310)	-0.0363** (0.0168)	0.0003 (0.0293)
US-Born				-0.4333*** (0.0974)	-0.4396*** (0.0966)
<i>Church</i> × <i>USBorn</i>				-0.0773** (0.0382)	-0.0952** (0.0386)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>					
<i>County</i> × <i>Year</i>		✓	✓	✓	✓
Ethnicity			✓		✓
R ²	0.1532	0.1628	0.1637	0.1633	0.1643
N	56,707	56,707	56,707	56,707	56,707

Notes: Standard errors are clustered at the county level. The ethnicity refers to immigrants who comes from one of the following countries of origin: Ukraine, Russia, Albania, Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia and Macedonia. The sample includes only individuals in workforce, where $15 < \text{age} < 64$. All models include County by Year fixed effects. The dependent variable is Log Wage, the natural logarithm of individual wages. The key independent variable is Church, numeric continuous variable for number of congregation of ethnicity in county. All specifications include Log Parental Income as a control variable. The sample includes individuals aged 15 to 64. Model specifications follow the same structure as in Table 1. Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

In the base model (Column 1), the coefficient on Church is -0.0432 and statistically significant at the 5% level.

using the diff in diff model (Column 2) the coefficient on Church becomes slightly more negative (-0.0546) and remains statistically significant at the 1% level.

when adding ethnic specific fixed effects to the regression (Column 3) the coefficient loses its significance, That raises concern that the results are driven by unobserved ethnic-specific characteristics rather than the presence of ethnic Orthodox churches themselves, and it possible that differences in wages could be more closely linked to inherent factors within specific ethnic groups, such as the historical patterns of labor market participation, educational attainment, or regional preferences of the group, rather than the bonding social capital effect of the churches.

In the interaction model (Column 4), the coefficient on Church remains negative (-0.0363) and statistically significant at the 5% level, while the interaction term between Church and US-Born is negative and significant, suggesting that the a

presence of church in a county is associated with loss of 3.6 percentage of personal income.

the interaction term stays the same in the last model with ethnic specific fixed effects but the coefficient on the base church variable becomes insignificant.

In our analysis, two instruments variables (IV) were used to address endogeneity concerns regarding the relationship between ethnic Orthodox churches and assimilation outcomes. we have used lagged values of church presence to rule out fear of reverse casualty and the distance to Eastern Orthodox churches in 1936 to rule out concerns of omitted variable that correlates within a county across time and effects drives our results. our findings are that, the validity of our selected instruments is questionable, and the results should be interpreted with caution.

C. Naturalization

Table (3) presents the results for citizenship as a proxy for social assimilation. In the base model (Column 1), the coefficient on Church are positive but statistically insignificant, but, in the diff in diff model (Column 2) the coefficient on Church becomes slightly negative (-0.0040) and statistically significant at the 1% level.

With the inclusion of ethnicity-specific fixed effects (Column 3), the coefficient remains negative at -0.0025 and statistically significant at the 1% level, indicating that the church presence continues to be negatively associated with citizenship even after accounting for ethnicity. In the interaction model (Column 4), the negative effect of Church persists, with a coefficient of -0.0035, suggesting that ethnic church presence hinders the naturalization process, particularly for first-generation immigrants. However, the interaction term between Church and US-Born is not statistically significant, implying no clear generational difference in this context. On average, across the specifications, the presence of ethnic churches in a county is associated with a decrease of approximately 0.3 percentage points in the probability of becoming a U.S. citizen, supporting the hypothesis that ethnic institutions may slow the process of social assimilation.

D. English Proficiency

Table (4) is structured similarly to the previous ones, using English proficiency as the outcome variable and proxy for assimilation. In contrast to the previous models, which anticipated higher integration for the first generation, we now expect that the presence of ethnic churches will have a negative effect on both first and second generations, with a stronger impact on the first generation. This is because language acquisition is closely tied to long-term integration, and the bonding social capital provided by ethnic churches is likely to hinder this process by increasing transaction costs associated with broader societal interaction.

In the first model, the coefficient on Church is 0.0075 and significant at the 1% level, suggesting that, on average, counties with ethnic churches have a slightly higher likelihood of English proficiency. However, when applying the difference-

Table 3—: Citizenship - Assimilation

Dependent Variable: Model:	(1)	(2)	Citizenship		
			(3)	(4)	(5)
<i>Variables</i>					
Church	0.0019 (0.0017)	-0.0040*** (0.0010)	-0.0038*** (0.0010)	-0.0020* (0.0011)	-0.0015 (0.0013)
US-Born				0.2733*** (0.0085)	0.2726*** (0.0085)
Church \times US-Born				-0.0097*** (0.0034)	-0.0098*** (0.0036)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>					
County X Year		✓	✓	✓	✓
Ethnicity			✓		✓
R ²	0.1577	0.1791	0.1814	0.1981	0.2002
N	72,774	72,774	72,774	72,774	72,774

Notes: Standard errors are clustered at the county level. The ethnicity refers to immigrants who comes from one of the following countries of origin: Ukraine, Russia, Albania, Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia and Macedonia. Sample includes citizens who eligible for citizenship, which are above age 21 and were at least 5 years in the United States. All models include County by year fixed effects. The dependent variable is Citizenship, a binary indicator equal to 1 if the individual is a U.S. citizen. The key independent variable is Church, numeric continues variable for number of congregation of ethnicity in county. The sample includes immigrants who have been in the US for at least 5 years or who are born in United States. Model specifications follow the same structure as in Table 1. Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

in-differences model in Column (2), the coefficient on Church turns negative (-0.0031) and remains statistically significant at the 1% level. This shift indicates that, once we control for time and county-specific effects, the presence of ethnic churches is associated with lower levels of English proficiency.

The addition of ethnicity fixed effects in Column (3) slightly reduces the coefficient's significance to the 10% level, but the overall negative relationship between church presence and language proficiency remains. After introducing interaction terms in Column (4), the coefficient on Church remains relatively unchanged in magnitude and becomes more statistically significant, though the interaction term itself is not statistically different from zero. When further controlling for ethnic group fixed effects in Column (5), all the coefficients, including the interaction term, become insignificant and are not statistically different from zero.

These results suggest that the presence of ethnic churches in a county is associated with a around 0.3 percentage point decrease in the probability of being proficient in English for the first generation immigrants, which supports our hypothesis. However, the evidence for the second generation remains inconclusive.

Table 4—: Ability to speak English - Assimilation

Dependent Variable:	English Proeficient				
Model:	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
<i>Variables</i>					
Church	0.0075*** (0.0021)	-0.0031** (0.0012)	-0.0025* (0.0014)	-0.0032** (0.0016)	-0.0024 (0.0018)
US-Born				-0.1997*** (0.0157)	-0.2016*** (0.0156)
Church × US-Born				-0.0032 (0.0033)	-0.0027 (0.0033)
<i>Fixed-effects</i>					
County X Year		✓	✓	✓	✓
Ethnicity			✓		✓
R ²	0.2236	0.2565	0.2604	0.2712	0.2752
N	96,352	96,352	96,352	96,352	96,352

Notes: Standard errors are clustered at the county level. The ethnicity refers to immigrants who comes from one of the following countries of origin: Ukraine, Russia, Albania, Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia and Macedonia. The sample include all individuals above age 5. All models includes County by Year fixed effects. The dependent variable is English Proeficient, Indicator variable for 'well' or 'very well' english level. The key independent variable is Church, numeric continues variable for number of congregation of ethnicity in county. The sample is the same as in Table 2. Model specifications follow the same structure as in Table 1. Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

E. Instrumental Variable

The first instrument results reported in table (??) in the apeendix, that variables utilized lagged values of church presence in period t-1 as instrument for church presence in period t, we find that the F-statistics of the first stage is exceptionally high across all specifications, with and without year, county and ethnicity fixed effects, and ranging from 12,460 to over 22,000.

such excessively high values raise concerns about multicollinearity, leading to distorted second-stage results. The large and significant negative coefficient on log wage (-0.0990) in the second-stage analysis further supports this concern. This magnitude of effect is unusually large and suggests that the model may be capturing spurious relationships rather than a true causal effect. One plausible explanation is that the lagged church presence is capturing time-invariant regional factors or trends that are not fully controlled for in the model, such as historical economic conditions, immigration patterns, or regional labor market dynamics. These underlying factors could be driving the strong first-stage relationship, but

they might not represent valid variation for identifying the true impact of church presence on assimilation outcomes.

The second instrument used the distance to the nearest Eastern Orthodox church in 1936. The first-stage F-statistics for this instrument ranged from 13.42 to 20.11, which is more in line with typical thresholds for instrument strength and suggests that this instrument is likely valid in terms of avoiding weak instrument bias. However, the second-stage results using this instrument are largely insignificant across most models, except for a marginally significant result on intermarriage.

The insignificant results across key assimilation outcomes (citizenship, wages, and English proficiency) may indicate that the distance variable is not a strong predictor of modern-day church presence, and hence lacks sufficient variation to drive a meaningful relationship with assimilation outcomes. The distant past (1936) may not be a strong determinant of current ethnic church networks, especially given the dynamics of immigration, demographic changes, and shifts in religious institutions over time. Moreover, the large positive coefficient on log wage (2.593) in the second-stage model is implausible and further highlights the limitations of this instrument in capturing the relevant variation.

For an instrument to be valid, it must satisfy two key assumptions: relevance and exclusion. While both instruments appear to be relevant in the first stage (as indicated by their F-statistics), their validity as exogenous instruments is more questionable. The lagged instrument likely suffers from over-identification and multicollinearity issues, inflating the estimated effects and reducing the credibility of the second-stage results. Meanwhile, the distance instrument may be weakly correlated with current church presence, and any significant results may be driven by noise rather than a true causal effect.

One critical challenge with both instruments is that they may be capturing long-standing regional characteristics that influence both church presence and assimilation outcomes, leading to omitted variable bias. For example, areas with historically high concentrations of immigrants may have more ethnic churches and lower assimilation outcomes due to persistent social and economic factors unrelated to the church's direct effect. These regional characteristics are likely not fully accounted for by the model, resulting in biased estimates.

V. Robustness Checks

A. Specification

the behavior of the model on the 2sls instrument raises concerns about the validity of the entire specification, since such high F-statistics points on overfitting of the model and potential multicollinearity issues. to handle that concerns and as robustness test we consider more simple model with simple diff in diff form, in that specification we use only 2010 and 2020 samples, of which the data is more consistent, we use dummy variable of the exposure to at least one church in

the county as the treatment and the 2020 year as the post period, such that the interaction term between church presence and post period will capture the effect of the church presence on the assimilation outcomes.

in addition, instead of including the Us-Born variable in the regression, we split the data into two samples, where, in the first sample, we include only the immigrant from our origin countries, and in the second sample, we include only the US-Born children of immigrant from our group. in that specification, we do not include citizenship for second generation sense we have very little variation, most of the second generation are US citizens.

o address concerns arising from the 2SLS estimation and as a robustness check, we employ a simpler difference-in-differences (DiD) model. This specification utilizes data from 2010 and 2020, periods with higher data consistency. We define treatment as the presence of at least one ethnic church in the county. The model is estimated separately for first-generation immigrants and their US-born children, excluding citizenship outcomes for the latter due to limited variation.

Our refined model specification is as follows:

$$(6) \quad Y_{icet} = \alpha_c + \gamma_e + \lambda_t + \beta_1 Church_c + \beta_2 (Church_c \times Post_t) + X'_{icet} \delta + \varepsilon_{icet}$$

where, Y_{icet} is the outcome for individual i in county c of ethnicity e at time t . α_c represents county fixed effects, γ_e denotes ethnicity fixed effects, and λ_t indicates time fixed effects. $Church_c$ is a dummy variable equal to 1 if county c has at least one ethnic church, 0 otherwise. $Post_t$ is a dummy variable equal to 1 for observations in 2020, 0 for 2010. X_{icet} is a vector of control variables including individual characteristics (e.g., age, education), county-level factors (e.g., average income, immigrant share), and ethnicity-specific county characteristics (e.g., ethnic group's population share), finally, ε_{icet} is the error term..

The coefficient of interest is β_2 , which captures the effect of ethnic church presence on assimilation outcomes. This DiD approach allows us to control for time-invariant county and ethnicity characteristics, as well as common time trends, while estimating the impact of ethnic churches on assimilation measures.

B. Results

The results of our difference-in-differences analysis are presented in Table 5. For the foreign-born sample, we observe a consistent negative effect of church presence on all assimilation outcomes except wages. Specifically, the presence of an ethnic church is associated with a 12.5 percentage point decrease in the probability of citizenship acquisition (column 1) and a 10.2 percentage point decrease in English proficiency (column 2), both significant at the 1% level. The effect on wages (column 3) is negative but statistically insignificant, with a large standard error. Interracial marriage (column 4) shows a similar magnitude of effect as citizenship, with a 12.6 percentage point decrease, also significant at the 1% level.

To isolate the effect of church presence from the duration of stay, we include years since migration as a control variable. Its positive and significant coefficients across outcomes suggest that the observed church effects are not driven by differences in time since migration. The consistency of the church presence effect, approximately 12.4 percentage points across outcomes, aligns with our hypothesis.

However, the magnitude of this effect raises concerns about potential omitted variable bias, particularly given the relatively low R^2 values. For the second-generation sample (columns 5-7), we find a significant effect only on intermarriage outcomes. Column 7 indicates that church presence is associated with a 1.3 percentage point decrease in the probability of intermarriage, significant at the 5% level. This effect, while smaller in magnitude, is consistent with our hypothesis and appears more plausible. The full regression results, including all control variables, are provided in the appendix for a more comprehensive analysis.

The assumption is parallel trends, which means that in the absence of the treatment (ethnic church presence), the trends in assimilation outcomes (citizenship, English proficiency, wages, and interracial marriage) would have been the same for both the treatment group (counties with ethnic churches) and the control group (counties without ethnic churches) within each ethnicity. and, that There are no other time-varying factors that differentially affect the treatment and control groups and are correlated with both the presence of ethnic churches and the assimilation outcomes.

The identification strategy relies on the parallel trends assumption, First, we assume that In the counterfactual scenario absent the treatment (i.e., ethnic church presence), the trajectories of assimilation outcomes—including citizenship acquisition, English language proficiency, wage progression, and interracial marriage rates—would have evolved similarly for both the treatment group (counties with ethnic churches) and the control group (counties without ethnic churches) within each ethnic cohort. Second, we assume that There exist no confounding time-variant factors that simultaneously differentially impact the treatment and control groups, and correlate with both the presence of ethnic churches and the assimilation outcomes under investigation.

These conditions, if satisfied, allow for the interpretation of the interaction term $Church_c * Post_t$ as the causal effect of ethnic church presence on assimilation outcomes, controlling for both time-invariant heterogeneity between groups and common temporal trends.

The parallel trends assumption in our difference-in-differences (DiD) model of ethnic church effects on assimilation outcomes relies on two key conditions. First, we assume that in the absence of ethnic churches, the trends in assimilation measures would be similar for counties with and without churches within each ethnic group. This assumption is strengthened by our use of ethnicity-specific comparisons, which control for broader ethnic trends. However, it may be challenged if counties where churches are established differ systematically from those without churches in ways that affect assimilation trajectories. For instance, pre-existing

community characteristics or immigration patterns that influence both church establishment and assimilation could violate this assumption. Moreover, the decision to establish a church may be endogenous to the assimilation process itself.

The second condition assumes no time-varying confounders that differentially affect treatment and control groups while correlating with both church presence and assimilation outcomes. While our county-level comparisons within ethnic groups help control for many potential confounders, this assumption could still be violated. Local economic shocks, changes as wars, or shifts in attitudes towards specific ethnic groups could differentially impact counties with and without churches while also affecting assimilation outcomes. those assumption, needs to be tested, but unfortunately, our data is limited to only two time points, and we those, so the interpretation of the results should be taken with caution.

Table 5—: Impact of Church Attendance and Time on Various Outcomes

Dep. Variable	Foreign Born				US Born		
	Citizen (1)	English (2)	Wage (3)	Marriage (4)	English (5)	Wage (6)	Marriage (7)
Church	0.094 (0.022)	0.010 (0.016)	0.186 (0.183)	0.057 (0.024)	0.346 (0.161)	2.586 (1.491)	0.748 (0.444)
Post	0.107 (0.039)	0.131 (0.030)	0.402 (0.322)	0.149 (0.044)	0.001 (0.308)	2.461 (2.182)	1.128 (0.583)
<i>Church × Post</i>	-0.125 (0.039)	-0.102 (0.030)	-0.292 (0.330)	-0.126 (0.045)	0.075 (0.312)	-2.754 (2.204)	-1.321 (0.596)
Years From Migration	0.009 (0.003)	0.003 (0.001)	0.001 (0.008)	0.003 (0.001)			
<i>N</i>	8924	10169	9666	6066	350	520	64
<i>R</i> ²	0.130	0.100	0.604	0.132	0.140	0.436	0.310

Signif. Codes: ***: 0.01, **: 0.05, *: 0.1

The table presents the results of a difference-in-differences analysis of the impact of exposure to at least one church of ethnicity in county on assimilation outcome. The ethnicity refers to immigrants who comes from one of the following countries of origin: Ukraine, Russia, Albania, Bulgaria, Romania, Serbia or Macedonia. First four columns are for the foreign-born sample, and the last three columns are for the children of immigrant who born in USA. The dependent variables are citizenship, English proficiency, wage, and interracial marriage. The key independent variables is the interaction term.

VI. Discussion

the work provides a nuanced examination of the role of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches in the assimilation of immigrants and their descendants in the United States. By leveraging county-level data and employing a difference-in-differences empirical strategy, we aimed to disentangle the complex effects of these religious institutions on various dimensions of assimilation, including social, economic, cultural, and civic outcomes.

One of the key strengths of the research lies in its focus on the Eastern Orthodox Church, an institution uniquely organized along ethnic lines. The organizational structure allows for a more precise analysis of how ethnic identity and religious affiliation intersect to influence assimilation processes. By including multiple ethnic groups—such as Russian, Ukrainian, Serbian, Albanian, Macedonian, Romanian, and Bulgarian immigrants—we broaden the scope beyond single-ethnicity studies, enhancing the generalizability of our findings.

Our empirical results present a mixed picture. On one hand, the presence of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches appears to facilitate certain aspects of social assimilation. For instance, the positive association between church presence and intermarriage rates suggests that these institutions may provide spaces for broader social interaction beyond the ethnic community. This challenges the notion that ethnic churches solely function as bonding social capital that hinders integration.

On the other hand, our findings indicate that ethnic church presence may impede other aspects of assimilation, particularly language acquisition and naturalization. The negative relationship between church presence and English proficiency implies that strong intra-group cohesion within ethnic churches might reduce incentives or opportunities for immigrants to acquire language skills essential for broader societal integration. Similarly, the negative association with citizenship rates suggests that these institutions may foster a stronger attachment to the country of origin, potentially delaying or reducing the pursuit of formal civic integration.

The analysis of economic assimilation yields inconclusive results. While some specifications indicate a negative effect of church presence on wages, the significance and magnitude of the effect diminish when controlling for ethnicity-specific fixed effects. This suggests that unobserved ethnic characteristics may play a substantial role in economic outcomes, and the direct impact of ethnic churches on economic assimilation may be limited or confounded by other factors.

Despite the contributions of the work, several weaknesses and limitations warrant discussion. First, the potential for selection bias remains a concern. Immigrants may self-select into counties with existing ethnic churches, or conversely, churches may be established in response to the needs of larger immigrant communities. This endogeneity challenges the causal interpretation of our results. Although we attempted to address the issue through fixed-effects models and instrumental variable approaches, the validity of our instruments—such as lagged church presence and distance to historical churches—may be questionable due to potential violations of the exclusion restriction.

Second, the reliance on county-level data may mask significant within-county heterogeneity. Counties vary widely in size and demographic composition, and aggregating data at the level may overlook important community-level dynamics. Future research could benefit from more granular data, possibly at the census tract or neighborhood level, to capture local variations in church influence and assimilation outcomes.

Third, the work’s focus on assimilation proxies—such as intermarriage, English proficiency, citizenship status, and wages—may not fully capture the multifaceted nature of assimilation. These measures, while informative, may be influenced by unobserved factors and may interact with each other in complex ways. For example, language proficiency can affect economic opportunities, which in turn may influence social integration measures like intermarriage.

Additionally, the temporal scope of the data poses limitations. With only three census years (2000, 2010, 2020), our ability to assess long-term trends and establish robust causal relationships is constrained. The use of lagged variables and historical instruments, while methodologically sound, may not fully account for dynamic changes in immigration patterns, church activities, or policy environments over time.

Another critical consideration is the potential impact of external events—such as political conflicts or economic crises—in the immigrants’ countries of origin or in the United States. Such events could influence both the establishment of ethnic churches and assimilation trajectories, introducing confounding factors not accounted for in our models.

Finally, the work could have delved deeper into the internal dynamics of the ethnic churches themselves. Understanding the specific activities, programs, and community outreach efforts of these institutions could shed light on the mechanisms through which they influence assimilation. Qualitative data or case studies might complement the quantitative analysis, providing richer insights into the lived experiences of immigrants within these religious communities.

In conclusion, while the work advances our understanding of the dual role of ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches in immigrant assimilation, it also highlights the complexity of disentangling the multifaceted influences of ethnic institutions. The findings underscore the need for a nuanced approach that considers both the supportive and potentially constraining effects of ethnic religious communities. Future research should aim to address the identified limitations, perhaps through longitudinal studies, mixed-methods approaches, or more sophisticated econometric techniques, to deepen our comprehension of how ethnic institutions shape the immigrant experience.

VII. Conclusion

Our findings contribute to the understanding of how ethnic Eastern Orthodox churches impact the assimilation of immigrants and their descendants in the United States. By employing a difference-in-differences empirical strategy and utilizing county-level data from the American Community Survey and the U.S. Religion Census, we were able to isolate the effects of these ethnic religious institutions on various dimensions of assimilation.

From a technical standpoint, we controlled for potential endogeneity and unobserved heterogeneity by incorporating county, year, and ethnicity fixed effects in our regression models. We also attempted to address selection bias and re-

verse causality through instrumental variable approaches, using lagged church presence and historical church locations as instruments. However, the validity of these instruments was questionable due to potential violations of the exclusion restriction, which we acknowledge as a limitation of our study.

Our robustness checks, including alternative specifications and interaction terms, provided mixed results. While some models indicated that ethnic church presence facilitates social assimilation through increased intermarriage rates, other models suggested a hindrance in language acquisition and naturalization processes. The inconsistency in our results highlights the complexity of disentangling the multifaceted influences of ethnic churches on assimilation outcomes.

In conclusion, while our findings offer valuable contributions to the literature on immigrant assimilation and the role of ethnic religious institutions, they also underscore the challenges inherent in measuring assimilation and isolating causal effects. Future research could benefit from more granular data, longitudinal studies, and the incorporation of qualitative methods to deepen the understanding of these complex dynamics.

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VIII. Appendix

A. Summary Statistics

B. Plots

Figure 1. : Share of Eastern Origin Immigrant By County

Source: ACS data. includes 2020 values of eastern Origin Immigrant share in each county

C. tables

Table 6—: Summary Statistics

Statistic	N	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max
<i>Outcome variables</i>					
intermarriage	96,352	0.076	0.265	0	1
Citizen	96,352	0.675	0.468	0	1
English Proficient	96,352	0.768	0.422	0	1
Log Wage	74,955	5.548	5.054	0.000	13.518
<i>Individual controls</i>					
Year	96,352	2,004.723	7.434	2,000	2,020
Age	96,352	37.879	24.226	0	95
Age squared	96,352	2,021.669	2,084.691	0	9,025
Age at Migration	76,772	25.816	17.740	-10	95
Educ Years	96,352	11.671	4.654	4	18
Years In US	76,772	18.537	17.420	0	91
Year Married	30,890	1,124.124	986.009	0	2,020
Migration Year	96,352	1,582.365	799.286	0	2,020
Us Born	96,352	0.203	0.402	0	1
Married	96,352	0.453	0.498	0	1
Unemployed	96,352	0.030	0.171	0	1
Log occupation score	96,352	1.757	1.678	0.000	4.394
Log wage Parent	37,263	8.238	4.095	0.000	13.402
<i>Church Variables</i>					
Congregations	96,352	0.499	1.359	0	18
Lag Congregations	30,890	0.567	1.498	0	18
Church	96,352	0.219	0.414	0	1
Adherent	96,352	311.021	1,854.265	0	30,870
Distance from 1936 Church	76,543	72,544.910	176,867.100	0.000	1,697,010.000
<i>County Controls</i>					
Population	96,352	86,699.190	106,675.800	612	471,162
Average Education years	96,352	11.590	0.687	8.993	14.189
Mean Unemployed	96,352	0.035	0.012	0.006	0.095
Mean log age	96,352	6.209	0.556	3.433	8.427
Mean log age Locals	96,352	4.740	1.196	2.430	7.399
Mean Occupational score	96,352	16.532	1.791	11.301	25.352
Share of immigrant	96,352	0.207	0.136	0.007	0.493
Share of Russian	96,352	0.005	0.007	0.000	0.026
Share of Serbs	96,352	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.008
Share of Macedonians	96,352	0.0003	0.001	0.000	0.007
Share of romanin	96,352	0.002	0.002	0.000	0.017
Ethnic group share	96,352	0.005	0.007	0.00000	0.027
Share of Black	96,352	0.136	0.114	0.000	0.658
<i>Ethnic-County Controls</i>					
Mean Ethnic Language isolated	96,352	0.248	0.185	0.000	1.000
Mean Occupational Score	96,352	15.186	4.649	0.000	80.000
Mean Education Years	96,352	11.671	1.593	4.000	18.000
Log Mean Ethnic Wage	96,133	5.597	1.593	0.000	13.225

Figure 2. : Number of Congregation By County

Source: Religion Census data. includes 2020 values of eastern Congregations in each county

D. Discussion

This paper partially realizes a promising idea by investigating the impact of church presence on immigrants from Yugoslavia during the Balkan Wars. The initial aim was to exploit the variation between nationalities within Yugoslavia to isolate the ethnic impact of the church, utilizing a unique context of the Balkan Wars that could be considered a natural experiment. To mitigate concerns about self-selection among immigrants, we initially focused on data from Germany and Austria—neighboring countries that received many refugees during the wars.

However, the scarcity of data and the difficulty in obtaining micro-level information on this population led us to abandon the pursuit of European data. This constraint compelled us to use data from the United States, where concerns about population selection bias are significantly greater, especially in such a late historical period. While the abundance of data available in the U.S. is advantageous, it does not offset the fact that U.S. immigration policy is non-random, even during periods of war and refugee intake.

In response to these challenges, we decided to leverage the ethnic diversity and unique characteristics of Eastern Orthodox churches more broadly, rather than focusing solely on the Serbian church. The ability to utilize a wide array of churches that are similar in religious attributes but differ in ethnic characteristics provided an intriguing avenue to isolate the ethnic component within the community framework. The Orthodox Church, managed in a highly hierarchical and conservative manner that responds slowly to temporal changes, presents a

Figure 3. : Lagged values of Congregation

Source: Religion Census data. Includes the number of Congregations of compared to previous year

valuable opportunity for natural experiments.

Moreover, the Orthodox Church has experienced internal schisms associated with connections to countries of origin. A notable example is the split of the Russian Orthodox Church into the Russian Orthodox Church Outside Russia (ROCOR) and the Russian Orthodox Church Patriarchate (ROC). This division occurred after the Communist Revolution in 1920. The churches reconciled in 1970 when ROCOR was recognized as an autocephalous church, with both bodies agreeing on jurisdictions over which the patriarchal church would have exclusive responsibility. Churches and parishes changed hands between these two entities based on policies established in the canonical bishops' assembly, a fact that holds significant implications for natural experiments.

ROCOR, with American roots, encourages integration and assimilation, whereas ROC is perceived as more conservative and ethnically oriented. This distinction

Table 7—: Census matched with ethnic orthodox church

Year	Ukrainian	Russian	Albania	Bulgarian	Romanian	Serbian	Macedonians
2020	670	1732	5	85	155	171	13
2010	1123	1940	18	42	360	320	30
2000	4785	10302	378	581	2789	1561	121
Counties Avalliable For 3 Periods	20	34	6	59	112	25	82

Notes: The table presents the number of counties matched with the orthodox church by ethnicity, list of all Churches Includes is in the apeendix

is reflected in the data presented in Table X in the appendices. Similar splits occurred in the Serbian, Macedonian, and Albanian churches, which divided into ethnic churches under the broader Orthodox Church following the Balkan Wars. The dissolution of the Soviet Union also holds considerable significance; immediately afterward, the patriarchal church expanded significantly. The recent conflict in Ukraine similarly bears relevance in this context.

These schisms and the unique features of the Orthodox Church present substantial potential for research in migration economics and economic history. However, capitalizing on this potential requires considerable investment and a thorough understanding of the jurisdictional structure of the Orthodox Church. While the Orthodox Church is remarkably well-documented, accessing and utilizing this data necessitates significant effort to comprehend its hierarchical structure, the decisions of its bishops, and the implications of these decisions in terms of ecclesiastical authority.

Furthermore, the churches are not entirely separate entities; most operate under the umbrella of the Orthodox Church, recognize one another, and collaborate under the Orthodox Church in America (OCA). In this paper, insufficient attention was paid to this interconnectedness, which may have implications for our analysis.

The paper succeeds in exploiting this context only partially, highlighting more of the research potential than its actual realization. In addition to the issues of inconsistency in our results and the problem of immigrant selection into the United States, there is a significant concern regarding selection bias related to the impact of ethnic churches. The true implication of our findings often is that ethnic churches tend to be established in areas with high concentrations of immigrants, and such areas are frequently economically disadvantaged.

Focusing on the children of immigrants was an attempt to mitigate this problem, but it was not entirely successful. The children are also subject to selection bias due to their parents' residential choices. Our difference-in-differences model suffers from a significant limitation: we have only three observations, each ten

Table 8—: Eastern Orthodox Churches in the USA by Ethnic Group and Year

Ethn	Labels	2000	2010	2020
Russian	Patriarchal Parishes of the Russian Orthodox Church	32	32	30
	Russian Orthodox Church Outside of Russia	129	146	199
Albanian	Albanian Orthodox Diocese of America	14	2	2
Serbian	Serbian Orthodox Church in North America	113	135	121
Bulgarian	Bulgarian Eastern Orthodox Diocese of USA	27	22	24
Ukrainian	Ukrainian Orthodox Church of the USA	104	101	89
Romanian	Romanian Orthodox Archdiocese in Americas	56	32	31
Macedonian	Macedonian Orthodox Church: American Diocese	17	20	20

The table shows the churches included in the analysis and the Ethnicity matching

years apart, making it challenging to assert that the parallel trends assumption holds. It is more plausible to assume that events such as the war in Ukraine have influenced the results in specific directions.

The use of historical data from the Census of Religious Bodies primarily serves to illustrate the possibility of exploiting path-dependent settlement patterns of institutions and their persistence over time. However, since we utilized cross-sectional data from 2020, it is difficult to derive substantive significance from these findings.

Another unaddressed issue, inherited from the paper we are replicating, is the problem of multiple hypotheses due to the proliferation of assimilation outcome variables. These are not proxy variables identical to a single construct but are correlated variables that influence and are influenced by one another, potentially also affected by omitted variables. For instance, naturalization is evidently dependent on an immigrant’s proficiency in English for both policy and practical reasons.

Both English proficiency and naturalization are influenced by marriage to a local American spouse. The directionality of influence among these variables is unclear, and assuming that they are all assimilation variables causally affected by the presence of ethnic communities is a difficult proposition. These variables interact in complex ways, collectively influencing immigrants’ positions within ethnic communities. ¹

¹Moreover, the original paper did not account for the fact that immigrants who wish to assimilate may choose to leave the city they initially settled in. The original study effectively examined the impact of Italian churches on immigrants who chose not to leave the county where the church was established, thereby introducing an additional assimilation bias.

The primary contribution of this paper lies in highlighting the unique context of the Eastern Orthodox Church, the persistence of its ethnic structure, and the attempt to exploit enduring institutional, cultural, and ethnic differences through historical patterns and their impact on migration economics. The unique context and the substantial investigative work on this subject constitute the most significant strengths of the paper.